

The diagonal-angle problem at a parallelogram

Harald Schröer

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Here we view a unknown problem. Both diagonals e, f and the angle β are known. We want to calculate the other quantities of the parallelogram.

We use the cosine law twice:

$$b^2 = \frac{e^2}{4} + \frac{f^2}{4} - \frac{1}{2} \cdot ef \cos \delta_1 \quad (1)$$

$$a^2 = \frac{e^2}{4} + \frac{f^2}{4} - \frac{1}{2} \cdot ef \cos \delta_2 \quad (2)$$

with $\delta_2 = 180^\circ - \delta_1$ and $\cos(180^\circ - \delta_1) = -\cos \delta_1$:

$$a^2 = \frac{e^2}{4} + \frac{f^2}{4} + \frac{1}{2} \cdot ef \cos \delta_1 \quad (3)$$

We use the cosine law once more:

$$e^2 = a^2 + b^2 - 2ab \cos \beta \quad (4)$$

The addition of the equations (1) and (3) yields the **sides-diagonals theorem** of the parallelogram:

$$2 \cdot (a^2 + b^2) = e^2 + f^2 \quad (5)$$

Now we insert in equation (4) the equation (5) for $a^2 + b^2$ and the equations (1) and (3) for b and a :

$$e^2 = \frac{e^2 + f^2}{2} - 2 \cos \beta \cdot \sqrt{\left(\frac{e^2 + f^2}{4} + \frac{ef \cos \delta_1}{2}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{e^2 + f^2}{4} - \frac{ef \cos \delta_1}{2}\right)}$$

or with $(a + b) \cdot (a - b) = a^2 - b^2$:

$$e^2 = \frac{e^2 + f^2}{2} - 2 \cos \beta \cdot \sqrt{\frac{(e^2 + f^2)^2}{16} - \frac{e^2 f^2 \cos^2 \delta_1}{4}}$$

Now we transform:

$$\frac{(e^2 - f^2)^2}{16 \cos^2 \beta} = \frac{(e^2 + f^2)^2}{16} - \frac{e^2 f^2 \cos^2 \delta_1}{4}$$

We solve to δ_1 :

$$\cos \delta_1 = \sqrt{\frac{\frac{(e^2 - f^2)^2}{4 \cos^2 \beta} - \frac{(e^2 + f^2)^2}{4}}{-e^2 f^2}}$$

simplified:

$$\cos \delta_1 = \frac{1}{2ef} \cdot \sqrt{(e^2 + f^2)^2 - \frac{(e^2 - f^2)^2}{\cos^2 \beta}}$$

and at last:

$$\cos \delta_1 = \frac{1}{2ef \cos \beta} \cdot \sqrt{\cos^2 \beta \cdot (e^2 + f^2)^2 - (e^2 - f^2)^2} \quad (6)$$

Thus δ_1 can be determined. It is valid $\delta_2 = 180^\circ - \delta_1$. With the equations (1) and (2) we can calculate b and a . We yield the area of the parallelogram with:

$$A = a \cdot b \cdot \sin \beta$$

Thus all quantities are calculated.

Cyclic permutation of equation (6) leads to:

$$\cos \delta_2 = \frac{1}{2ef \cos \alpha} \cdot \sqrt{\cos^2 \alpha \cdot (e^2 + f^2)^2 - (f^2 - e^2)^2} \quad (7)$$

We multiply out the radicand of equation (6):

$$(\cos^2 \beta - 1) \cdot e^4 + 2e^2 f^2 \cdot (\cos^2 \beta + 1) + f^4 \cdot (\cos^2 \beta - 1)$$

With $\sin^2 \beta + \cos^2 \beta = 1$:

$$= 2e^2 f^2 \cdot (2 - \sin^2 \beta) - \sin^2 \beta \cdot (e^4 + f^4)$$

We use the identity $e^4 + f^4 + 2e^2 f^2 = (e^2 + f^2)^2$:

$$= 4e^2 f^2 - \sin^2 \beta \cdot (e^2 + f^2)^2$$

Thus we get:

$$\cos \delta_1 = \frac{\sqrt{4e^2 f^2 - \sin^2 \beta \cdot (e^2 + f^2)^2}}{2ef \cos \beta}$$

With cyclic permutation:

$$\cos \delta_2 = \frac{\sqrt{4e^2 f^2 - \sin^2 \alpha \cdot (e^2 + f^2)^2}}{2ef \cos \alpha}$$

With the fact that the radicand cannot be smaller than zero it follows for the parallelogram:

$$4e^2 f^2 - \sin^2 \beta \cdot (e^2 + f^2)^2 \geq 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \sin \beta \leq \frac{2ef}{e^2 + f^2}$$

and

$$4e^2 f^2 - \sin^2 \alpha \cdot (e^2 + f^2)^2 \geq 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \sin \alpha \leq \frac{2ef}{e^2 + f^2}$$

At last we become acquainted with a second proof of the sides-diagonals-theorem:

We use again the cosine law:

$$e^2 = a^2 + b^2 - 2ab \cos \beta$$

$$\Rightarrow \cos \beta = \frac{a^2 + b^2 - e^2}{2ab}$$

It is valid: $\alpha + \beta = 180^\circ$ and

$$\cos \alpha = \cos(180^\circ - \beta) = -\cos \beta \tag{8}$$

We can express f with the cosine law as well:

$$f^2 = a^2 + b^2 - 2ab \cos \alpha$$

Now we insert the term of $\cos \beta$ in $\cos \alpha$, at which we use equation (8):

$$f^2 = a^2 + b^2 + 2ab \cdot \frac{a^2 + b^2 - e^2}{2ab}$$
$$\Rightarrow f^2 = a^2 + b^2 + a^2 + b^2 - e^2$$

It follows again the sides-diagonals-theorem:

$$e^2 + f^2 = 2 \cdot (a^2 + b^2)$$

References

- [1] Harald Schröder "Trigonometric problem cases well solved" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2001